

Reductio ad Hitlerum: Reflections on the Russian Propaganda of de-Nazification in Ukraine

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Abstract

In the second lecture delivered at the University of Chicago in 1949, political philosopher Leo Strauss postulated *reductio ad Hitlerum* as a variant version of *reductio ad absurdum*. The inherent assumption of the argument is that the use of *reductio ad Hitlerum* as a justification procedure is a substitute maneuver for not having sound and plausible arguments. Because *reductio ad Hitlerum* is simply an all-and-nothing signifier, President Putin deceptively misquotes de-Westernization, de-Ukrainization and Russification as de-Nazification occurrences of his 'special military operation' in Ukraine. In fact, what Putin purports to achieve through the de-Nazification of Ukraine as defensive justification turns into outright Nazi behavior-like actions as a mechanism of defensive response. This article is ultimately a reflection on the puzzling meanings of the Russian de-Nazification strategies in Ukraine. Following brief methodological considerations on the above-mentioned stratagem and the explanation of the Russian approach of de-Nazification in Ukraine, three distinct sections - i.e., de-Nazification as de-Westernization, de-Ukrainization, and Russification, respectively - scratch out Putin's official rationale for the invasion of Ukraine. A coda of this examination is added to explain that 'Putinism 3.0' is the subsequent result of the Russian *reductio ad Hitlerum* propaganda and actions in Ukraine. The final section also argues that Putin's geopolitical imaginary is the last stage consistent with 'Putinism 3.0', and the arbitrary versions of de-Nazification (i.e., de-Westernization, de-Ukrainization and, respectively, Russification) are intermediate stages only.

Keywords

reductio ad Hitlerum; de-Nazification; de-Westernization; de-Ukrainization; Russification; Putinism 3.0

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Introduction

In the second lecture delivered at the University of Chicago in 1949, political philosopher Leo Strauss (1953: 42-43) postulated *reductio ad Hitlerum* as a specious version of *reductio ad absurdum*. The inherent assumption of the argument is that the use of *reductio ad Hitlerum* as a justification procedure is a substitute maneuver for not having sound and plausible arguments. Moreover, the instrumentalization of *reductio ad Hitlerum* through the propaganda of de-Nazification could apparently work to legitimize violent actions and conceal real intentions. The current flow of events in Ukraine is the perfect instantiation of the Russian obscurantism and manipulative strategies regarding the de-Nazification of its neighboring country. Its perplexity notwithstanding, the Russian propaganda of de-Nazification in Ukraine is derived from the ideological laboratory of projecting onto Ukrainians what Putin and the Kremlin ideologues are *de facto* pursuing in Ukraine. In other words, the pseudo-justification criterion of *reductio ad Hitlerum* is Putin's and his acolytes' most appropriate catalyst for instituting destruction and chaos, distorting common-sense perceptions, and misleading the world regarding real actions and goals. Because *reductio ad Hitlerum* is simply an all-and-nothing signifier, President Putin has deceptively misquoted de-Westernization, de-Ukrainization and Russification as de-Nazification solutions.

The scope of the present investigation is to advance an alternative – and, hopefully, a more plausible – reading of the actual motivations and goals of Russia in Ukraine, behind the 'smoke curtain' of the Russian propaganda on de-Nazification. Accordingly, the following reflections attempt to dissect the mystifications of the Russian propaganda consistent with the *reductio ad Hitlerum* procedure of justification, and to reveal that this mechanism of projection and defense turns against Putin and Russians themselves. Specifically, what Putin purports to achieve through the de-Nazification of Ukraine as defensive justification turns into outright Nazi behavior-like actions as a mechanism of offensive response. Ultimately, these thoughts aim to showcase that the misleading strategies of de-Nazification in Ukraine are used to conceal Russia's real intentions regarding its errand into the new world of politics. Three sections - i.e., de-Nazification as de-Westernization, de-Ukrainization, and Russification, respectively - scratch out Putin's official justifications for the invasion of Ukraine and attempt to lay bare a more plausible rationale. A coda of this examination is added to explain that 'Putinism 3.0' is the subsequent result of the Russian *reductio ad Hitlerum* propaganda and actions in Ukraine. The final section also argues that Putin's geopolitical imaginary is the last stage consistent with 'Putinism 3.0', and that the arbitrary versions of de-Nazification (i.e., de-Westernization, de-Ukrainization and, respectively, Russification) are intermediate stages only.

The puzzling approaches of the Russian de-Nazification of Ukraine

The strategy of *reductio ad Hitlerum* illuminates on the likelihood of understanding Vladimir Putin's infamous 'special military operation' speech of February 24, 2022. In his 28 minutes address to the Russian nation, the President of the Russian Federation issued his *de facto* declaration of war on Ukraine and grounded it on purportedly compelling justifications of de-Nazification, de-militarization and defense of the Russian minority and language in Ukraine (Putin, 2022). Cynically tailored to camouflage personal resentment and anger regarding what he has perceived as Russia's post-Imperial, late-Soviet, and post-1990 continuous decline (Tsygankov, 2015: 19), Putin's statements resorted to emotionalism and psychologism according to ad hominem, personalistic, and neo-sovereigntist perceptions of power politics. To foment support of Russians and deter international counteractions for his muscular politics in Ukraine, in absence of realistic and compelling motivations, President Putin activated a projection mechanism of justification. Emotionally, the Russian President singled out de-

Nazification for two main reasons. Firstly, he aimed to stir negative passions of Russians in confronting the revivalism of the Nazi ideology in Ukraine. Secondly, President Putin planned on delivering a compulsory substitute for rational justifications regarding the fight against the so-called 'Ukronazism' (Timofey Sergeytsev). Psychologically, the Russian president projected the Nazi conundrum in Ukrainians while denying it in himself (Baumeister, Dale, and Sommer, 1998), and associated it with a strategy of consciously misdirecting intentions, distorting facts, and manipulating audiences. While the emotional rationale is used as a justification for the defense of the Russian nation, the psychological mechanism serves as justification for the offensive response. In other words, de-Nazification has become the emotional vehicle for the justification of Russia's defense against exogenous dangers, and aggressiveness as offensive response has transformed Putin's Russia into a genuine Nazi perpetrator.

The tricky strategies of Ukrainian de-Nazification are fabricated with a view to distort facts and values, and to generate a pervasive atmosphere of disorientation and misunderstanding. The very mechanism of projecting certain Nazi traits and actions in Ukrainians spotlights on Russian hidden actions and agenda, transforming *reductio ad Hitlerum* into a ubiquitous category of explanation and understanding rather regarding the actions of Russians than the characterization of Ukraine. In this way, *reductio ad Hitlerum* turns into a kind of a far-fetched and radiant halo on Russification and Putinism. Using de-Nazification as a salient rationale, Russia's war against Ukraine is a spiral downward to outright Nazism, humanitarian disaster, and total destruction (Walzer, 1977: 21-33). The forfeited Russian rhetoric on Ukrainian de-Nazification has the effect of reawakening in reverse the horrific politics of Germany in the late 1930s in Czechoslovakia and Austria, grounded on biopolitical justifications of ethnic purity and preservation of identity. Starting from the false premise of Ukrainian de-Nazification, anything goes: distortion of historical past and present, fabrication of truth and facts, sordid propaganda, and deceitful justifications. After all, who buys the story of Ukraine dominated by the neo-Nazi ethos of the Azov Movement (John and Lister, 2022) more than crediting the far-right Kremlin politics conducted through neo-Nazi organizations, such as the Wagner Group, Ruskiei Obraz or Night Wolves? (Soufan and Sales, 2022). In the realm of fictional constructions of reality, common-sense becomes the exception and the anomaly is converted into substantive and truthful narration.

Ultimately, *reductio ad Hitlerum* could be admitted as a working hypothesis only in full acknowledgement of the unfinished and speculative project of Nazism. Logically, in order to accurately grasp the meanings of de-Nazification, one should have to accurately appropriate the facets of historical Nazism and Nazification. Understood as an uncompleted experiment in totalitarianism (Gentile and Mallett, 2000), Nazification could be used as an epithet to depict recurrent phenomena specific to German Nazism within the ideological portrayal of a political regime, while de-Nazification could be rendered to fighting and exterminating the demon once and for all. The internal inconsistencies and irresoluteness of the Nazi ideology stem from a plethora of speculative options which amalgamate pseudo-scientific theories of state management, biopolitics and strategic expansionism that have never succeeded to coagulate a comprehensive and coherent doctrine. Essentially assimilated to an experiment in power politics to the detriment of policymaking, Nazism remains abstract, puzzling, and unconsummated. Since the Nazis themselves disagreed on the significance of Nazification (Caplan, 1980: 51), followers and opportunists have taken momentum to re-enfranchise its mantra according to their ends and interests. Putin's vilification of Ukraine plentifully epitomizes the ideological inconsistency and temporal displacement of Nazism with a view to instate his geopolitical dreams (Smith, 1986: 14-16).

Dismantling the *Volkstum*: reductio ad Hitlerum to pursue de-Westernization

Within the scope of the present interpretation, Russia's actions in Ukraine unveil a three-stage processual undertaking in the form of an algorithm towards Russia's geopolitical profiling – the last stage of the process. In line with the Russian outlook, the first two steps seem to be not only preliminary, but also necessary. Firstly, since 2008 if not earlier, Putin's propaganda has been targeting the *Volkstum*, or the community of people in Ukraine. Strikingly similar with the aims of pan-Germanism during the Nazi regime, in the footsteps of Herder and Fichte (Frøland, 2020: 32-38), Russia seems to aim at the pulverization of all horizontal bonds of Ukrainian communities, including state administration, political and civil societies, economic ties, etc. Especially in the aftermath of 2019 Ukrainian elections, Putin's Russia has started to gradually lose control over the already-divided territory of Ukraine after the 2014 annexation of Crimea and separatism of Donbas, and maniacally invoked identity threats. Russia has constantly pinpointed the West (i.e., the United States of America and the European Union) as the dividing enemy, so that the Russian plan to restore the horizontal ties between Ukraine and Russia would be tantamount to de-Westernize Ukraine. Specifically, not only Ukrainian "pro-western scum and traitors" (Troianovski, 2022) must be eliminated, but also liberals, democrats, secular humanists, Jewish global elites, feminists, and all the values associated with the Western model of civilization and progress. According to Putinist Russia, all these Western traits bear the stigmas of "decadence, weakness and impurity" (Stanley, 2022). The similitude with the Nazi tribulations against European nations, liberal democracy and parliamentarism in the 1930s is obvious.

Through Putin's lenses, Ukraine has embarked on following the West's dubious morality grounded on secular modernization and steady progress. Since the Western creed is decadent and illusory, the mission of Russia is to firstly achieve a pragmatic awakening by signaling the dangers of degradation and degeneracy of Ukrainian institutions and communitarian values. In the very spirit of the Nazi ideology in the 1930s (Bialas, 2014: 15-19), Russia counterposes an ethnocentric-oriented morality grounded on Russian national ethos to the detriment of internationalist humanism and feeble morality, and higher values to the detriment of common-sense rationality. An emancipated and 'westernized' Ukraine would be the equivalent of entering the carousel of self-destruction. In occurrence, Russian officials have strongly denounced what they deemed as the "orange plague" of the 2008 Orange Revolution in Ukraine (a reference to the "brown plague" of patriotic Hitlerism), and what they explicitly associated with the "fascist spirit" of the 2014 Euro-Maidan protests (Stallard, 2022), both inspired by the West. In the eyes of Putin and his acolytes, Russophobia Ukrainian nationalists have ignited pro-European passions in the aftermath of 2008, and the Euro-Maidan acme in 2014 has contributed to accelerating the trend. On the other hand, strong evidence suggests the hypothesis that the Russian delirium about the pro-European Ukraine has been constantly fueled by Donbas separatists, Russian monarchists and orthodox nationalists, Stalinist and Cossack devotees in Russia (Fried, 2022; Holzer, Laryš and Mareš, 2018).

Putin's endorsement of a principled opposition between the Slavic / Russian values and the Western creed has always underlined the subtext of Russian economic and geopolitical interests. On the one hand, from a pragmatic standpoint, Russia's regional and geopolitical interests have collided with Ukraine's aspirations to join NATO and benefit from Western security guarantees; in the aftermath of 2004 Ukrainian elections, Russia has constantly attempted to block Ukraine's pro-Western moves and prevent further Eastward expansionism of NATO mainly by using economic chantage. In order to secure Russia's regional and geostrategic interests, Putin used the instrument of economic incentives and pushed Ukraine to extend the lease agreement on Russia's Black Sea fleet until 2042. On the other hand, Russia has exerted its enormous potential of economic intimidation by

exploiting Ukraine's dependence on Russian energy and trade. The Russian energy-goliath Gazprom steadily moved to gain energy monopoly in the East and acquired 50% stake of the Belarusian Beltransgaz in 2007 but failed to take control of the Ukrainian Naftogaz. Moreover, Ukraine temporarily escaped Putin's clutching tentacles by denying affiliation to the Russian-coordinated Customs Unions organization in 2011 (Tsygankov, 2015). The overall dissenting spirit of Ukraine has generated irritation in Russia and impelled Putin to increased aggressiveness. In addition, Putin blamed the West for abetting the Ukrainian non-compliance; his rhetoric reiterates the diatribe of two unofficial Nazi ideologues, Alfred Rosenberg and Dietrich Eckart, against the Western financial and economic goals of domination in Germany (Lane, 1974: 14-15).

Since 2008, uncertainty and confusion among Ukrainians coupled with the high risk of losing Ukraine have stimulated Putin to conduct assertive maneuvers in order to prevent the neighboring country's split from Russia. A 2013 survey revealed that 50% Ukrainians were favorable to strengthening ties with Russia, while the other half inclined towards the West (Charap and Darden, 2013). Under the circumstances and considering the fragile pro-Russian inclinations of Ukrainians, President Putin has been compelled to take the bull by the horns and increase interference with Ukrainian internal affairs and exert constant pressure upon the Ukrainian government and influential elites. His Nazi-variety stratagem of dismantling the *Volkstum* ultimately speaks about the horizontal instauration of a "politicized society" as a form of overarching "control over governmental administration, economic life, and public opinion through the use of propaganda, personnel control, and administrative influence" (Orlow, 1973: 13-14).

The Russian-style politicization of the Ukrainian society at large has been acknowledged as the first strategic move to eliminate pro-Western impetuses, connections, and expectations of Ukrainians. The first stage of the Ukrainian de-Nazification utterly stands for the Russian attempts to excoriate what the Western ideological and political agendas have contaminated in Ukraine: the drives for freedom of expression and civic protests, democratization of political processes and public institutions. These drives have gradually transformed nascent empirical contents of Ukrainian politics (i.e., political participation and democratization of political institutions and behaviors) to the point of their incompatibility with related practices in Russia. Confronted with the Ukrainian disobedience and non-alignment, Putinist Russia has perceived the gradual Westernization of Ukraine as a solid threat to its traditional political culture. However, the Russian leader was wise enough to understand that the acquisition of 'body politics' and government mechanisms would not guarantee the acquisition of the 'Ukrainian soul'. The transition towards the next strategic plan has been further precipitated by the regime change in the aftermath of 2019 Ukrainian elections. Accordingly, a second stage of annihilation was envisaged in order to effectively enforce what the Russian propaganda nefariously called the 'solution of the Ukrainian question' (Akopov, 2022).

Annihilating the *Volksgeist*: reductio ad Hitlerum to pursue de-Ukrainization

Considering Putin's arcane justifications for his 'special military operation' in Ukraine, it is rather conjectural to establish what segment of the Ukrainian society is more dangerous and antagonistic towards the Russian interests. Is there the category of cosmopolitan internationalists, pluralists and democrats, or the groups of ultra-nationalists and fundamentalist patriots that are envisioned as the key target of the Russian ideological drive for the purge of undesirables? In other words, what types of ideological groups and individuals pervert more the primeval 'Russian soul' and more substantially betray the spiritual ties between Russians and Ukrainians? In the way in which the Nazi ideologue Gregor Strasser criticized Germany's ideological weaknesses in the 1920s, Putin's cryptic assertions

about the Ukrainian ideological traitors arrogate a change of spirit rather than a systemic change of politics in Ukraine. Accordingly, the takeover of the community of people (*Volkstum*) should be followed by the loftier approach to the redemption of the community of spirit (*Volksgeist*), i.e., the annihilation of the 'Ukrainian soul' and the regeneration of the 'Russian soul'. Disputing over the authenticity of their 'original soul' and the characteristics of their distinct core values, Russians and Ukrainians have unfolded ingenuous narratives of continuity / discontinuity and activated / deactivated appropriate elites for the purpose of defending specific stories (Moulioukova and Kanet, 2022: 115).

Within the above-mentioned context of the battle of narratives, the Russian propaganda of de-Nazification has gained momentum. Leaving aside intricate historical sodalities and divisions between the two countries before the formation of the Soviet Union, and the Russian epic of the true Russian soul's origins as early as the end of the ninth century in Kievan Rus, the 'grand narratives' of the two countries counterpose Ukrainian (ultra)nationalists to condescending Russophiles. The Achilles heel of the controversy resides on Russia's claims that Ukraine is an artificial nation and that the Ukrainian soul betrayed and perverted the true spirit of Russianism especially during the Great Patriotic War (i.e., the Second World War), whereby Ukraine experienced a transitory episode of Nazism. Logically consistent with the controversy on Russia's de-Nazification of Ukraine in the aftermath of February 24, 2022, the Ukrainians have reprimanded the Russian actions of ethnic cleansing and genocide, while the Russians have invoked the necessity of total elimination of neo-Nazi factions (such as the Azov Movement and Patriot of Ukraine) and Banderites (fanatics and worshippers of WWII Ukrainian hero Stepan Bandera and other Nazi zealots, such as Roman Shukhevych and Yaroslav Stetsko) (Miller, 2018; Rudling, 2020). Once more, de-Nazification as de-Ukrainization reveals not only Russia's Nazi-type of aggressive response, but also a ruthless belligerence to conclusively vanquish the 'Ukrainian soul'. Augmenting Putin's rhetoric use of demilitarization as a camouflaged argument for the incapacitation of Ukraine's security and obliteration of self-determination, de-Nazification as de-Ukrainization is specifically directed to the lustration of the Ukrainian community of spirit.

The radical argument used by the Russian propaganda is that the Ukrainian nation and spirit do not exist, or – if it exists – the 'Ukrainian soul' is essentially Nazi-contaminated and oriented. Consequently, to achieve de-Ukrainization is tantamount to effect de-Nazification. As Nazism has been associated to horrors, destruction and catastrophe, Putin probably hoped to induce empathy worldwide so that de-Nazification should be acknowledged not only as legitimate vindication, but also as a permanent value to be defended (Holborn, 1964: 547). If the de-Nazification strategy of the West in post-war Germany urged for re-education of elites and the German people to consciously acknowledge the atrocities of the Nazi regime, the Russian officials explicitly endorse liquidation and lustration, since they disseminate the narrative according to which re-education is not possible (Sergeytsev, 2022, cited in Brown, 2022). By adopting an uncompromising version of de-Nazification, Russia seems to emulate the Nazi-centered agenda based on racial cleansing and eugenics in the 1930s and 1940s Germany. At the very core of de-Nazification as de-Ukrainization is the concept of identity purgation.

Since there is no compelling evidence than the phenomenon of Nazism in Ukraine has turned rampant to become the dominating spirit of Ukrainians, the strategy of Russia resorts to a kind of metonymical identification of a minor segment of the Ukrainian society (i.e., the neo-Nazis) with the whole society. This tricky maneuver serves as a hardline justification for the comprehensive purgation of identity in Ukraine instead of a more focused approach to eliminate only the Neo-Nazi factions. A

softer version of the identity cleansing rhetoric resorts to chrono-topical arguments according to which the inconsistent Ukrainian identity is in fact entrapped between the more robust Polish-based identity in Western Ukraine and the Russian-based identity in Eastern Ukraine (Molioukova and Kanet, 2022: 127). Tantalized in their frenzy of de-Nazification, the Russian Putinists go as far as to plea for the de-Nazification of other six counties of the former Soviet bloc (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland and Kazakhstan) (Savostyanov, 2022, cited in Goble, 2022). Moreover, the Russian anti-Nazi hysteria pointed to neo-Nazi Western groups specifically trained and financed to fight against Russia in Ukraine and to experimental biological laboratories created by the Pentagon in Ukraine to produce pathogenic Nazism! (Yarovaya, 2022). Unfortunately, concomitant with the writing of these lines, the Russian battle to conquer the purportedly Nazified Ukrainian spirit results in massive war crimes and genocide. Bucha, Mariupol, and Severodonetsk have symbolically re-enacted the darkest times of the second world war. The security scapegoat and the Russian gripe against the dissolution of Russianness in Ukraine have turned into the apogee of “Russian chauvinism against Ukrainians”, who are ultimately “a branch of Russian people” (Kuzio, 2017: 16, 46).

By and large, Putin’s ‘thaumaturgy’ of purifying the Ukrainian soul moves beyond scratching out the surface layers of Western borrowings. It goes deeper with a view to purge the incurable Ukrainian soul. Ultimately, Putin’s strategy of Ukrainian de-Nazification claims that the Westernization of Ukraine has gradually increased simply because the Ukrainian soul is utterly damaged and must be cleansed. The de-Nazification of Ukraine in the third stage (i.e., Russification) is only possible by starting in a ‘clean slate’. In other words, the *tabula rasa* approach of de-Nazification in Ukraine works as a prerequisite of restoring Russification by completing the stages of dismantling the *Volkstum* and annihilating the *Volksgeist*, respectively.

Securing the *Lebensraum*: reductio ad Hitlerum to complete Russification

In addition to de-Westernization and de-Ukrainization, the strategic shenanigan of *reductio ad Hitlerum* in Ukraine has been maliciously conceived by Russia in order to achieve substantive Russification. Once achieved, a robustly ‘Russified’ Ukraine turns into a prerequisite of two main Russian goals according to the calculations of Putin’s blueprint. Regionally, Russia will be able to secure its Slavic *Lebensraum*, necessarily – but not sufficiently – including Russia, Belarus, and Little Russia (i.e., Ukraine). Geopolitically, Russia will be able to play the upper hand within the Eurasian dreamworld. Thus, Russification logically follows two previous stages: de-Westernization (i.e., suppression of Ukrainian sovereignty and political institutions, pulverization of civil society and control of public opinion, curtailment of democratic aspirations and liberal mentalities) and de-Ukrainization (i.e., obliteration of Ukrainian nationhood and patriotic sentiments, annihilation of Ukrainian identity and values). Notwithstanding common-sense rationality and compelling justifications, the Russian mavericks have overplayed the malapropism of de-Nazification because they hoped to reawaken the opprobrium of Nazism and, consequently, to emotionally manipulate domestic and international public opinion. In reality, this hoax is possible because of the very erratic nature of the term ‘de-Nazification’ that could be used as a bricolage instrument to justify any strategic decision and action. For this reason only, Putin could *de facto* push forward his aggressive campaign in Ukraine, ceaselessly invoking de-Nazification as the alpha and omega of all possible justifications. Because de-Nazification stands for anything and nothing at once, it can be used as a vicarious justification when needed.

Analytically instrumental to Russification, de-Nazification cannot be procedurally separated from the strategic actions of the Russian Federation. In practice, de-Nazification has been planned by the Russian propaganda as a set of aggressive actions to achieve Russification. Seemingly fascinated

with the dictum ‘the end justifies the means’, the Russian propagandists tend to overlook the fact that the path to Russification is adorned with war crimes and humanitarian disaster. In its urge for de-Westernization and de-Ukrainization, Putin’s Russia ungraciously walks over dead bodies for the ultimate goals of conserving the Russian heritage, inducing the ‘Russian way’, and promoting the airy principles of the Eurasian geopolitics (Eltchaninoff, 2018). Yet, procedurally, the Russian ‘grand strategy’ is barbaric and utterly absurd. One could not consistently defend the outright atrocities of de-Nazification ‘special operations’ in the name of the abstract values of Russification. The connection between the two will always remain traumatic in nature and will haunt both Russians and Ukrainians. On the one hand, the de-Nazification of Ukraine in preparation of Russification includes liquidation of elites and opposition, mass investigations, war tribunals, decoupling from the Western civilizational creed, erasure of all tenets of Ukrainian identity – nationhood, history, memory, values, language, etc. On the other, the Russian self-assumed mission of re-education after de-Nazification points to restoration of historic Russia, ideological censorship, Russification of Ukrainian public institutions, instauration of the Russian information space, a new constitution, etc. (Petrenko, 2022). The Putinist version of integral Russification has become more and more evident after 2008, by the time when Putin had already managed to absorb the Russian nationalist forces represented by clear-cut Russophiles, such as Vladimir Zhirinovskiy and Dmitriy Rogozin. Moreover, in official discourses, Putin has deliberately replaced the moderate term *Rossiyskiy* with the more fundamentalist and ethnicist reference to *Russkiy* in the aftermath of 2014 Euromaidan turmoil (Tsygankov, 2015: 15-16).

In truth, Putin’s de-Nazification as Russification has been concocted to refurbish and propel Russia as a significant global power. The regional small-scale rhetorical repertoire contains references to Russia’s concern for securitization of its regional *Lebensraum*. In line with the definition of the doctrine as securitization of national survival through the expansion of the living space, the Russian version of *Lebensraum* has been configured as the purgation of undesirables and dissenters from its territory by enforcing methods of authoritarian ruling (Smith, 1986: 92-93). Rejuvenating the theories of Halford Mackinder and Karl Haushofer according to which “the ‘heartland’ of Eastern Europe and Russia ensured its rulers a wider dominance in the world” (Godrick-Clarke, 2004: 220), Putin has enduringly ruminated about the self-preservation of the Russian identity and the expansion of Russia’s territorial living space. Even Aleksandr Solzhenitsyn, the outstanding Soviet dissident, saluted Putin’s concern for restoring the whole Russian nation. ‘Holy Russia’, the by-product of centuries of suffering and self-sacrifice, must be preserved by any means possible, including biopolitical strategies of fostering a certain identity to the detriment of diversity and multiculturalism (Langdon and Tismăneanu, 2020: 128-129). The *Russkiy Mir* (Laruelle, 2015: 12) and *Novorossiia* (Toal, 2017: 239-243) presently epitomize *Lebensraum* versions of Putin’s strategy of regional consolidation in the service of his geopolitical imaginary.

Ultimately, de-Westernization, de-Ukrainization and Russification have been tailored to fit the big picture utopia of Putin’s arrogance. Apparently, the Russian leader’s defensive speeches on the necessity of securing the Russian *Lebensraum* only are at odds with outright *Weltpolitik* aspirations. In fact, Putin’s actions in Transnistria, Georgia, Syria, and Ukraine are only preparatory calisthenics for Putin’s assertiveness in the global arena, mirroring the macro-political thinking of Russian ultranationalists and Eurasianists, such as Aleksandr Dugin, Aleksandr Prokhanov, or the think-tank Izborsk Club. Specifically, what Putin and Russian Putinists are ultimately trying to achieve is the membership of the Russian power in the select club of the twenty-first century geopolitical powers. It goes without saying that Putin himself is annoyed by the geopolitical narratives about the United States-China competition and strives for the return of the Russian ‘prodigal son’ in the twenty-first

century muscular politics. Very much in the spirit of the Nazis in the 1930s, the Russian Putinists are escalating the doctrine of national eschatology with a view to instill the Russian geopolitical reawakening (Varshizky, 2012). Putin's perception that the West has repeatedly acted to "sweep [Russia] into a corner" (Putin, 2014) and the Russian hardline voicing of Eurasian endeavors are conducive towards the redrawing of the geopolitical map according to Russian ambitions.

What Putin and Putinists fundamentally fail to understand is that Russia has ceased for more than three decades to pursue a consistent and convincing public diplomacy; instead, Russia's surrogate diplomacy has vacillated between diplomacy of fear and petty authoritarianism. Unlike the United States' and China's robust moves in the fields of grand strategy politics and public diplomacy, Russia's 1999 'Millennium Manifesto', for instance, was received with skepticism and has failed to 'win hearts and minds'. The self-aggrandizement of Putin's geopolitical intuitions has faded away in humdrum inaccuracy and sheer psychosis.

Coda. Putinism 3.0. and the misdirecting logic of de-Nazification in Ukraine

President Putin's geopolitical ambitions (Putinism 3.0.) chronologically follow his domestically autocratic ruling (Putinism 1.0.) and his attempts to consolidate Russia's regional security (Putinism 2.0.). Except for President Putin and his ideological acolytes, nobody could really grasp the substantive meanings of his politics of Ukrainian de-Nazification, apart from its instrumentalization for illusory ends. Rather used as a 'Trojan horse' to pursue an imperialist agenda, the de-Nazification of Ukraine turns into a fraudulent maneuver of reckless Putinism 3.0. Because Putinists started to realize that de-Nazification cannot be used as an effective diplomatic asset, the Russian peace negotiators did not include it on their end of March 2022 agenda of negotiations in Turkey. Failing to convert the cynical rhetoric gambit into genuine truth claims, Putinism 3.0. bargains *reductio ad Hitlerum* beyond right and wrong, or truth and lie criteria of acceptability. Putin's post-truth Russia is the equivalent of a Putinist-like suspension of reality, whereby "boundaries between fact, opinion and fabrication disappear, and with them disappears the stability of a shared reality" (Roudakova, 2017: 219). De-Nazification epitomizes the twist of understanding and reality roll-over and could only be rendered to narrow-minded ethnic nationalism and malleable populism. Outside Russia, what is perceived as an arbitrary criterion of justification for geopolitical domination turns into a solid domestic rationale, in a country (i.e., Russia) where Putinism seems to have suppressed political contestation. Improvised political thinking based on Machiavellian de-Nazification has transformed the lethargic Russian bear into the Putinist beast. According to the Putinist logic of de-Nazification, truth is converted into self-glorifying rhetoric and the international legal norms are obliterated by the mantra of ethno-political justice. In line with this description, Putinist Russia perfectly embodies "a state of political exception" (Sakwa, 2020: 59-60).

Notwithstanding its logical and intelligibility frailties, the geopolitical teleology of Putinism 3.0. ultimately contrives the integral Russification of Ukraine and mischievously uses de-Nazification as its puzzling instrument. Logical inconsistency makes Putinism unintelligible and cruel, while rhetorical deviousness contributes to the overall embezzlement of its doctrinarian traits. In this way, Putinism is logically void and rhetorically relativistic. In the latter respect, more specifically, it is simply appalling to notice that Putinism twists conventional meanings of words into contrarian ones. The vocabulary of Putinism is a mysterious rhetorical trickery in transliteration and meaning distortion. Accordingly, there is more than using de-Nazification as a ubiquitous reference to anything and nothing at once: the semantic ultra-relativism of Putinism reads aggression as self-defense, outright declaration of war as 'special military operation', disinformation and propaganda as self-revealing truths, etc. Imposture

and historical relativism may transform the common-sense rebuttal of Nazism as a tribute to the Holocaust memory into a symbolic reiteration for the defense of ‘Russianness’! Dismantling language and in-stating semantic schizophrenia, one could easily find himself/ herself living in an alternative world. For instance, one finds out that the invasion of Ukraine has not brought about instability and humanitarian disaster, but – to the contrary – the promised stability of the Russian world. According to Putinism 3.0., this is the best of all possible worlds.

References

- Akopov, P. (2022). The Advent of Russia and the World. *RIA Novosti Agency*, February 26 [online]. Available at <http://www.aalep.eu/advent-russia-and-new-world>.
- Baumeister, R.F., Dale, K., & Sommer, K.L. (1998). Freudian Defense Mechanisms and Empirical Findings in Modern Social Psychology: Reaction Formation, Projection, Displacement, Undoing, Isolation, Sublimation, and Denial. *Journal of Personality*, 66(6), 1081-1124. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6494.00043>
- Bialas, W. (2014). Nazi Ethics and Morality: Ideas, Problems, and Unanswered Questions. In W. Bialas, & L. Fritze (Eds.), *Nazi Ideology and Ethics* (pp. 15-56). Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Brown, C. (2022). A Kremlin paper justifies erasing the Ukrainian identity, as Russia is accused of war crime. *CBC News*, 5 April [online]. Available at: <https://www.cbc.ca/news/world/kremlin-editorial-ukraine-identity-1.6407921>.
- Caplan, J. (1980). Recreating the Civil Service: Issues and Ideas in the Nazi Regime. In J. Noakes (Ed.), *Government, Party, and People in Nazi Germany* (pp. 34-56). Exeter: University of Exeter Press.
- Eltchaninoff, M. (2018). *Inside the mind of Vladimir Putin*. London: C. Hearst and Co.
- Fried, D. (2022). Putin’s ‘denazification’ claim shows he has no case against Ukraine. *Politico*, 1 March [online]. Available at: <https://www.politico.com/news/magazine/2022/03/01/ukraine-russia-history-distortion-denazification-00012792>.
- Frøland, C.M. (2020). *Understanding Nazi Ideology: The Genesis and Impact of a Political Faith*. Jefferson, North Carolina: McFarland & Company.
- Gentile, E., & Mallett, R. (2000). The sacralization of politics: definitions, interpretations, and reflections on the question of secular religion and totalitarianism. *Totalitarian Movements and Political Religion*, 1(1), 18-55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14690760008406923>.
- Goble, P. (2022). Moscow deputy says besides Ukraine, Russia must ‘de-Nazify’ six more countries. *Eurasia Review*, 3 May [online]. Available at: <https://www.eurasiareview.com/03052022-moscow-deputy-says-besides-ukraine-russia-must-de-nazify-six-more-countries-oped/>.
- Goodrick-Clarke, N. (2004). *The occult roots of Nazism: secret Aryan cults and their influence on Nazi ideology*. London and New York: Tauris Parke Paperbacks.
- Holborn, H. (1964). Origins and Political Character of Nazi Ideology. *Political Science Quarterly*, 79(4), 542-554. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2146698>.
- Holzer, J., Laryš, M., & Mareš, M. (2018). *Militant right-wing extremism in Putin's Russia: Legacies, forms and threats*. London: Routledge.
- John, T., & Lister, T. (2022). A far-right battalion has a key role in Ukraine’s resistance. Its neo-Nazi history has been exploited by Putin. *CNN*, 30 March [online]. Available at: <https://edition.cnn.com/2022/03/29/europe/ukraine-azov-movement-far-right-intl-cmd/index.html>.

- Kuzio, T. (2017). *Putin's war against Ukraine: Revolution, nationalism, and crime*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.
- Lane, B.M. (1974). Nazi ideology: Some unfinished business. *Central European History*, 7(1), 3-30. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0008938900010451>.
- Langdon, K.C., & Tismăneanu, V. (2020). *Putin's totalitarian democracy: Ideology, myth, and violence in the twenty-first century*. Cham, Switzerland: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Laruelle, M. (2015). *The Russian world: Russia's soft power and geopolitical imagination*. Washington DC: Center on Global Interests.
- Miller, C. (2018). In Ukraine, ultranationalist militia strikes fear in some quarters. *Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty*, 30 January [online]. Available at: <https://www.rferl.org/a/ukraine-azov-right-wing-militia-to-patrol-kyiv/29008036.html>.
- Molioukova, D., & Kanet, R.E. (2022). The battle of ontological narratives: Russia and the annexation of Crimea. In R.E. Kanet, & D. Molioukova (Eds.) *Russia and the world in the Putin era: From theory to reality in Russian global strategy* (115-139). London and New York: Routledge.
- Orlow, D. (1973). *The history of the Nazi party, 1933-1945*. Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Petrenko, R. (2022). 'Russian propagandists' decisions on what to do to Ukraine: re-education, censorship, and de-Ukrainisation. *Ukrayinska Pravda*, 4 April [online]. Available at: <https://www.pravda.com.ua/eng/news/2022/04/4/7337056/>.
- Putin, V. (2014). *Address by President of the Russian Federation* [online]. Available at: <http://eng.kremlin.ru/news/6889>.
- Putin, V. (2022). *Address by the President of the Russian Federation* [online]. Available at: <http://en.kremlin.ru/events/president/news/67843>.
- Roudakova, N. (2017). *Losing Pravda: Ethics and the press in post-truth Russia*. Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Rudling, P.A. (2020). *Tarnished heroes: The Organization of Ukrainian Nationalists in the memory politics of post-Soviet Ukraine*. Stuttgart: ibidem Press.
- Sakwa, R. (2020). *The Putin Paradox*. London and New York: I. B. Tauris.
- Sergeytssev, T. (2022). What should Russia Do with Ukraine? *RIA Novosti Agency*, 3 April [online]. Available at <https://ria.ru/20220403/ukraina-1781469605.html>.
- Smith, W.D. (1986). *The ideological origins of Nazi imperialism*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Soufan, A., & Sales, N. (2022). One of the worst ways Putin is gaslighting the world on Ukraine. *NBC News*, 6 April [online]. Available at: <https://www.nbcnews.com/think/opinion/putin-nazi-pretext-russia-war-ukraine-belied-white-supremacy-ties-rcna23043>.
- Stallard, K. (2022). The truth about Putin's 'denazification' fantasy. *The New Statesman*, 2 March [online]. Available at: <https://www.newstatesman.com/world/europe/ukraine/2022/03/the-truth-about-putins-denazification-fantasy>.
- Stanley, J. (2022). The antisemitism animating Putin's claim to denazify Ukraine. *The Guardian*, 26 February [online]. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2022/feb/25/vladimir-putin-ukraine-attack-antisemitism-denazify>.
- Strauss, L. (1953). *Natural right and history*. Chicago & London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Toal, G. (2017). *Near abroad: Putin, the West, and the contest over Ukraine and the Caucasus*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Troianovski, A. (2022). Why Vladimir Putin invokes Nazis to justify his invasion of Ukraine. *The New York Times*, 17 March [online]. Available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/03/17/world/europe/ukraine-putin-nazis.html>.

- Tsygankov, A. (2015). Vladimir Putin's last stand: the sources of Russia's Ukraine policy. *Post-Soviet Affairs*, 31(4), 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1060586X.2015.1005903>.
- Varshizky, A. (2012). Alfred Rosenberg: the Nazi Weltanschauung as modern gnosis. *Politics, Religion & Ideology*, 13(3), 311-331. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21567689.2012.698977>.
- Walzer, M. (1977). *Just and unjust wars: a moral argument with historical illustrations*. New York: Basic Books.
- Yarovaya, I. (2022). The Pentagon's activities in Ukraine are parts of a political, economic, military and biological occupation. *The State Duma*, 10 June [online]. Available at: <http://duma.gov.ru/en/news/54578/>.